

Exploring the publication metadata fields in Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions: Possibilities and ease of doing scientometric analysis

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Abstract

Publication of a large number of research papers during the last few decades motivated creation of scholarly databases for indexing the publications and recording citations. The publication metadata fields in scholarly databases are now retrieve for various purposes ranging from information search to research evaluation. Traditionally Web of Science and Scopus have been major database sources used. However, with the creation of newer databases like Dimensions, the choice has expanded further. The coverage and citation data of the major databases have been compared in many previous studies. However, there is no existing work on comparison of metadata fields provided by the scholarly databases. This work, therefore, attempts to bridge this research gap by comparing the metadata fields contained in the data downloaded from Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions. The effect of existence or absence of a metadata field in a database on the possibilities and the ease of doing scientometric analysis is explored. The findings are useful for scientometric researchers, practitioners and database managers.

Keywords: Dimensions, Metadata, Scholarly Databases, Scientometrics, Scopus, Web of Science.

Introduction

The massive growth in scholarly outputs during the last few decades has resulted into creation of several scholarly databases to index the outputs. The Web of Science, Scopus, Google Scholar etc. are few prominent scholarly databases in use today. These databases are now used for a number of purposes ranging from article retrieval to research assessment. Traditionally, research assessment exercises in scientometric studies have more frequently drawn research output data from one of the two well-known scholarly databases- Web of Science or Scopus. The research assessment exercises use metadata stored in the databases in several ways. The scientometric research assessment exercises comprise computing different metrics such as author-level metrics, publication-citation trends, national/international collaboration patterns, open access status of research, social media coverage, citation network, journal-level metrics, funding status of institutions/countries etc. In order to compute these metrics and to do scientometric analysis, one needs to obtain metadata for selected research publications from a scholarly database.

The access to metadata of a database usually requires some kind of subscription. For example, Web of Science and Scopus databases can be accessed through a subscription. These subscriptions may have varying privileges. While some allow only user interface-based access, few advanced subscriptions may allow API based access to the database. The databases allow that the required metadata can be downloaded in different file formats such as csv, excel, BibTex, RIS etc. The appropriate file format is chosen according to the type of analysis as well

as according to the software package to be used for analysis and visualization. For example, the BibTex or RIS formats can be easily used with visualisation software like VOS viewer (Van Eck & Waltman, 2017), Pajek (Batagelj & Mrvar, 1998), Gephi (Bastian, Heymann & Jacomy, 2009) etc. In case, a more advanced programming language-based analysis is to be done, the csv and excel may be more suitable formats. Thus, there exists a choice in terms of data format and sometimes also in terms of type of access (user interface-based or API-based).

The publication metadata downloaded from the scholarly databases usually contain data classified under various fields. These may include metadata for authors (such as author name, ORCID id, email address, researcher id etc.), organization (such as city/state/country details of the affiliating organization), publication type (such as journal article, conference proceeding, book chapter, letter, erratum, preprint, article in press etc.), publication source (such as source journal name, book name, conference name, publisher, publisher address, ISSN, eISSN etc.), citation (such as total citations received, cited references, relative/field citation ratio etc.), funding details (such as funding organization, funding text, grant ids etc.), and subject classification (such as broad research area and detailed subject category) etc. Other commonly provided fields include doi, language, publication id, publication year etc.

Several previous studies have done a comparative analysis of different databases (such as Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016; Harzing & Alakangas, 2019; Martin-Martin et al., 2021; Visser, van Eck & Waltman, 2021; Singh et al., 2021a) and have shown that the databases vary significantly in their coverage. It has also been seen that due to variations in the coverage of databases, the scientometric analysis on data obtained from different databases are found to provide varying evidence (Singh et al., 2021b). However, there are virtually no studies on comparison of the metadata fields contained in the databases and the impact that they may have on the scientometric research exercises. This study, therefore, attempts to explore the variation in metadata fields provided by different databases and what impact such variation may have on the possibilities and ease of doing scientometric analysis. More precisely, the following research questions are attempted to be answered:

RQ1: What are the major metadata fields in data obtained from UI based search in Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions and how much do the metadata fields differ across databases?

RQ2: Do the variation in metadata fields from the three databases result in different possibilities and ease of doing various scientometric analysis?

The metadata fields provided by the three major scholarly databases- Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions- are analysed. Only these three scholarly databases are considered as they are the major curated databases being used at present. For the reasons of uniformity of analysis, we have used the metadata fields provided by the user interface-based access of the three databases for analysis.

The study is not only novel and unique but also important and useful for scientometric researchers and practitioners. The analysis of metadata fields provided by the databases informs what scientometric analysis can or cannot be done with data from a given database. The analysis also informs about the ease of doing specific scientometric analysis if the data is taken from a particular database. Thus, the researchers and practitioners interested in a specific scientometric analysis can use the knowledge and select a suitable database as data source for the analysis. Further, the findings can be used by database designers and managers in improving the structure, organization and access of the databases.

A brief overview of the three scholarly databases

This section provides a very brief overview of the three databases (Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions). For a more detailed information, articles in the special issue of *Quantitative Science Studies*¹ may be referred to (Birkle et al., 2020; Baas et al., 2020; Herzog, Hook & Konkiel, 2020).

Web of Science

Web of Science, the oldest among the three scholarly databases, has originated from the work on citation index created by Eugene Garfield from the Institute of Scientific Information (ISI) in 1955. The Science Citation Index (SCI) initially covered 700 journals. It has grown thereafter, and a new citation index- Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) was added in 1973 followed by Arts & Humanities Citation Index (AHCI) in 1978. These three citation indices were launched together as Web of Science in 1997. A new index for books called Book Citation Index (BKCI) was added in 2011. The most recent addition in the list is the Emerging Sources Citation Index (ESCI) launched in 2015 with an aim to provide early visibility for titles being evaluated for inclusion in the classical indices- SCIE, SSCI, and AHCI (Somoza-Fernández, Rodríguez-Gairín, & Urbano, 2018). Currently, Web of Science is owned by Clarivate Analytics².

As per the latest data³, around 85.9 million scholarly data and 1.9 billion cited references (dating back to 1900) across 254 subject-disciplines is covered by the Web of Science Core Collection. The Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE) indexes 9,200 journals across 178 scientific disciplines comprising of total 53 million records and 1.18 billion cited references; the Social Sciences Citation Index (SSCI) indexes 3,400 journals across 58 social sciences disciplines comprising of total 9.37 million records and 122 million cited references; and the Arts & Humanities Citation Index (AHCI) indexes 1,800 journals across 28 Arts & Humanities disciplines comprising of total 4.9 million records and 33.4 million cited references.

Web of Science provides a subscription-based access for search and retrieval of data. The data search on the UI interface of Web of Science includes Basic Search, Advanced Search, Author Search and Cited References Search. In the Advanced Search tab, query formulation using Web of Science search tags and Boolean operators is enabled. The data can be downloaded in various formats such as, tab delimited, excel, plain text, RIS, BibTex formats etc. Moreover, sorting search results via certain options is also available, for example the results of a query can be sorted in ascending/descending order of publication date, highest citations received, relevance etc. There is also a provision of API based access to database, however it is not provided as part of the standard user interface-based access.

Scopus

Scopus database, a product of Elsevier, was created in 2004. It is often referred as one of the largest expert-curated scholarly databases that covers scientific journals, books, conference proceedings etc. which are selected through a process of content selection followed by continuous re-evaluation. The decision to index a journal or conference or other publications is taken by a Content Selection and Advisory Board (CSAB). Unlike, Web of Science, it has a single citation index, covering journal and conference articles in different subject areas.

¹<https://www.mitpressjournals.org/toc/qss/1/1>

²<https://clarivate.com/webofsciencegroup/>

³<https://clarivate.com/webofsciencegroup/solutions/web-of-science-core-collection/>

At the time of launch of Scopus in 2004, around 27 million publication records were indexed for the period 1966-2004. As of now, publication records from the year 1788 onwards are covered, with an addition of approximately 3 million records every year. The recently updated content coverage of Scopus shows that it comprises of 25,100 active journal titles, more than 210,000 books from 5000 international publishers and over 9.8 million conference papers from over 120,000 worldwide events. The Scopus content coverage guide⁴ indicates that it contains a total of over 77.8 million core records.

Scopus platform allows data access by Search (Basic and Advanced), Discover and Analyse options. The Basic Search option contains Documents, Authors, Researchers Discovery and Affiliations search while the Advanced Document search enables formulation of a query using Scopus field codes and Boolean operators to search in the Scopus database. The feature for sorting the search results is also available on Scopus platform, for example the results of a query can be sorted in ascending/descending order of publication date, highest citations received, relevance etc. The Discover option enables users to identify collaborators, research organizations with respect to research output, finding related publication data through various metrics such as author keywords, shared references etc. The Analyse option is a tool to track citations, assessment of search results on criteria such as country wise, affiliation wise, research area wise distribution of resultant data. Data can be retrieved from Scopus in various file formats like csv, BibTex, Plain Text, RIS etc. In addition to access through UI, Scopus also provides an API-based access as part of higher-level subscription.

Dimensions

Dimensions database was created in 2018 and is a relatively newer database as compared to Web of Science and Scopus. As indicated in its launch description which says, “*it brings together data describing and linking awarded grants, clinical trials, patents and policy documents, as well as altmetric information, alongside traditional publication and citation data*” (Herzog, Hook & Konkiel, 2020), it provides a single platform to access different kinds of research data. Dimensions, being the most recent and drawing data from different sources, has quite rich data about institution ids, grant ids etc. Unlike Web of Science and Scopus, Dimensions uses a different approach for sourcing data, with Crossref and PubMed being the “*data spine*”. The *bottom up* approach used indicates that the data sourced from Crossref and PubMed is further enhanced by collecting data about affiliations, citations etc. The data enhancements are done through a data enhancement process that takes data from various sources such as DOAJ, initiatives like Open Citations and I4OC, clinical trial registries, openly available public policy data, and other Digital Science companies like Altmetric and IFI Claims.

The launch version of Dimensions in 2018 contained about 90 million publications (out of which 50 million has full text records), with greater than 873 million citation links (Hook, Porter & Herzog, 2018). According to the latest data updates⁵, Dimensions contains 130 million publications (from around 104,000 journals, 63 preprint servers and 1.5 million books) with about 1.6 billion citation links. Additionally, it indexes data on 6 million grants, 12 million datasets, 226 million online mentions, 883,000 policy mentions, 724,000 clinical trials and 149 million patents.

Dimensions provides different types of access to users such as Dimensions free version, Dimensions Analytics, Dimensions Profiles, Dimensions on Google BigQuery and Dimensions

⁴https://www.elsevier.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0007/69451/Scopus_ContentCoverage_Guide_WEB.pdf

⁵<https://www.dimensions.ai/dimensions-data/>

for Life Sciences & Chemistry with different levels of privilege attached with each of them. The user interface-based search enables searching for a particular query in Full Data, Title and Abstract and DOI along with Filters like searching in a particular year or time period, researcher name, research categories, publication type etc. Data from Dimensions can be downloaded in different formats such as csv, excel, BibTex and RIS. Dimensions also allows an API based access which provides more advanced features.

Related work

Scientometric research assessment exercises have traditionally drawn data from scholarly databases like Web of Science and Scopus. During the last few years many new databases have come up, such as Dimensions, Microsoft Academic (relaunched recently as OpenAlex) etc. The studies on comparison of different databases started with the creation of Scopus and Google Scholar databases (Mayr & Walter, 2007; Gavel & Iselid, 2008; Lopez-Illescas et al., 2008, 2009; Vieira & Gomes, 2009). While Mayr & Walter (2007) compared a German journal list in Social Sciences across Web of Science and Google Scholar databases, Gavel & Iselid (2008) analysed the overlaps between Web of Science (WoS) and Scopus and some other major scientific databases. Lopez-Illescas et al. (2008,2009) performed an Oncology journal list comparison and their impact on publication-citation trends of countries across Web of Science and Scopus databases. Vieira & Gomes (2009) worked on coverage and overlap between Web of Science and Scopus for university domain (for a set of Portuguese universities) for the year 2006. A comprehensive comparison of title coverage, presence of language biases in journal coverage across Web of Science and Scopus was done in studies like Chadegani et al. (2013), Mongeon & Paul-Hus (2016). Web of Science, Scopus & Google Scholar were longitudinally compared on 8 data points on a sample of academicians across different disciplines by Harzing & Alakangas (2016). Scholarly databases like PubMed, Scopus & Web of Science were analysed on parameters such as coverage, focus and tools using Jordanian authors data across few disciplines by AlRyalat, Malkawi & Momani (2019). Similarly, Aksnes & Siversten (2019) compared Web of Science & Scopus on publication type, field of research and language on Norwegian authors data.

Citation-related studies on scholarly databases has also been an active area of exploration among researchers. Citation patterns comparison across popular scholarly databases like Web of Science, Scopus & Google Scholar on research published by Library and Information Science faculties was performed by Yang & Meho (2006). Falagas et al. (2008) compared PubMed, Google Scholar, Scopus & Web of Science on citations accrued in the field of Biomedical Research. Torres-Salinas, Lopez-Cózar & Jiménez-Contreras (2009) performed citation comparison across Web of Science & Scopus on data in Health Sciences for a Spanish University. Similarly, Web of Science & Google Scholar were compared on citation dataset from 3 UK Business Schools by Mingers & Lipitakis (2010). Macro and micro-level comparison for environmental sciences' journals in South Africa across Web of Science, Scopus & Google Scholar was performed by Adriaanse & Rensleigh (2011, 2013). De Winter & Dimitra Dodou (2014) compared Web of Science & Google Scholar in development of citation counts in diverse research fields, real growth vs retroactive growth. Studies like Martin-Martin et al. (2018), Martín-Martín, Orduna-Malea & López-Cózar (2018) have performed a comparative analysis of Google Scholar, Web of Science and Scopus for highly cited documents in different subject areas.

The newer databases like Dimensions, Microsoft Academic etc. have also been explored in various respects in the recent studies. Dimensions database was explored as an alternative to the popular scholarly databases like Web of Science and Scopus by Thelwall (2018a).

Microsoft Academic, Dimensions, Crossref, Web of Science, Scopus & Google Scholar were explored and compared on publication-citation trends in a single academic and six top journals in Business & Economics by Harzing (2019). Huang et al. (2020) performed a bibliographic comparison of Microsoft Academic, Web of Science & Scopus at institutional level considering data from 15 universities. Visser, van Eck & Waltman (2019) compared Dimensions, Crossref, Web of Science & Scopus through publication record match. A comparative analysis of citations to English-language highly cited documents from 252 subject categories in Google Scholar, Microsoft Academic, Dimensions, OpenCitations' COCI, Web of Science & Scopus was performed in the study by Martin-Martin et al. (2021). Visser, van Eck & Waltman (2021) performed a direct as well as pair-wise comparison of Dimensions, Crossref, Microsoft Academic, Web of Science databases with Scopus database on scientific articles. A comprehensive journal coverage comparison using the Master Journal Lists of 3 popular academic databases Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions was performed in a study by Singh et al., (2021a). Recently, a work by Maddi & Badoin, (2022) analysed the completeness of author-address links in the Web of Science database during the years 2000 & 2020.

Despite there being several previous studies on various aspects of scholarly databases, the metadata fields provided by these databases have not been analysed. The structure and availability of metadata decides what kind of scientometric analysis can be done and with what ease. Given the fact that the possibilities and ease of doing scientometric assessment is likely to be dependent on the metadata provided by the scholarly database, it is very important that an analysis of the metadata provided by various databases be done. However, to the best of our knowledge there are no existing studies on comparison of metadata fields provided by the three databases and there lies the research gap that this study attempts to bridge.

Data & method

The analysis being focused on the metadata fields, the metadata fields in the data downloaded from the three databases were identified. For this purpose, the metadata fields were obtained by downloading some publication records by formulating queries in the UI interface of the respective database. The publication metadata fields in Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions remain the same whether data is downloaded for any search topic, author, journal, particular year or range of years, institution, or a country (this was verified by doing multiple search queries). Therefore, a query on the topic "Artificial Intelligence" was made in all the three databases. In the UI interface of Web of Science database, the search query was TS="artificial intelligence", where TS stands for Topic Search. Similarly, the search query in Scopus was TITLE-ABS ("artificial intelligence") and in the Dimensions database, the term "artificial intelligence" was searched in the UI interface by limiting search to title and abstract. The publication metadata for the first 100 records was downloaded for each case. From the downloaded records, the metadata fields provided were identified.

The data downloaded from Web of Science contained data classified under 68 metadata fields. The data downloaded from Scopus comprised 43 metadata fields, while the publication data downloaded from Dimensions (through UI search) comprised of 71 metadata fields. Some examples of metadata fields in Web of Science are- PT (for Publication Type), DOI (for Digital Object Identifier for a publication), DT (for Document Type), AU (for Authors), C1 (for Address of the Author's affiliating organization), PY (for Publication year of a document) etc. Scopus data comprised metadata fields like Authors (Authors of the publication), Title (Title of the publication), Source title (Journal in which the document is published), DOI (Digital Object Identifier of the publication), Cited by (Total no. of citations received by the publication) etc. The Dimension database has metadata fields like Rank (Relevance ranking of

the publication), Publication ID (unique ID provided by Dimensions to each publication), Title (Title of the publication), Abstract (Abstract of the publication), PubYear (Publication year of the document), Open Access (Open Access status of the publication), Author (Authors of the publication) etc.

The metadata fields identified in the three databases were then grouped into different categories for further analysis. The major categories created include metadata for article details, author details, research organization details, publication source details, citation and usage details, funding acknowledgement details, textual details, open access details, conference details, subject category details. For each of the categories, the metadata fields provided by the three databases were identified. Thereafter, the possibilities of scientometric analysis that can be done from the available metadata fields in each of the three databases were identified. Subsequently, the ease of doing different scientometric analysis from the available metadata fields of various databases were explored. The figure 1 provides an illustration of the data and steps of the analysis.

Figure 1: Data sources and methodology

Analysis and discussion

The metadata fields provided in the data downloaded from user interface-based search in the three databases Web of Science were identified and categorised into different groups.

The data downloaded from Web of Science contains data classified under 68 metadata fields, such as PT (for Publication Type), DOI (for Digital Object Identifier for a publication), DT (for Document Type), AU (for Authors), C1 (for Address of the Author’s affiliating organization), PY (for Publication year of a document), AB (for Abstract of a publication), TI

(for Title of a publication), LA (for language of the publication) etc. The complete set of metadata fields provided in the Web of Science UI downloads is shown in Figure 2.

PT, AU, BA, BE, GP, AF, BF, CA, TI, SO, SE, BS, LA, DT, CT, CY, CL, SP, HO, DE, ID, AB, C1, RP, EM, RI, OI, FU, FX, CR, NR, TC, Z9, U1, U2, PU, PI, PA, SN, EI, BN, J9, JI, PD, PY, VL, IS, PN, SU, SI, MA, BP, EP, AR, DI, D2, EA, PG, WC, SC, GA, UT, PM, OA, HC, HP, DA

Figure 2: Metadata Field tags in Web of Science

The data downloaded from Scopus comprises of 43 fields such as Authors (Authors of the publication), Title (Title of the publication), Source title (Journal in which the document is published), DOI (Digital Object Identifier of the publication), Cited by (Total no. of citations received by the publication) etc. The complete set of metadata fields found in data downloaded from Scopus UI are shown in Figure 3.

Authors, Author(s), Title, Year, Source title, Volume, Issue, Art. No., Page start, Page end, Page count, Cited by, DOI, Link, Affiliation, Authors with affiliations, Abstract, Author keywords, Index keywords, Molecular Sequence Numbers, Chemicals/CAS, Tradenames, Manufacturers, Funding Details, Funding Text 1/2/3.., References, Correspondence Address, Editors, Sponsors, Publisher, Conference name, Editors, Sponsors, Publisher, Conference name, Conference date, Conference location, Conference code, ISSN, ISBN, CODEN, PubMed ID, Language of Original Document, Abbreviated Source Title, Document Type, Publication Stage, Open Access, Source, EID

Figure 3: Metadata Fields in Scopus

The publication data downloaded from Dimensions through UI search comprises of 71 fields, such as Rank (Relevance ranking of the publication), Publication ID (unique ID provided by Dimensions to each publication), Title (Title of the publication), Abstract (Abstract of the publication), PubYear (Publication year of the document), Open Access (Open Access status of the publication), Author (Authors of the publication) etc. The metadata for obtaining Cited References of the publication can be downloaded by exporting data for bibliometric mapping in csv format (option available in Dimensions data export). The complete set of metadata fields provided in data downloaded from Dimensions user interface-based search is presented in figure 4.

Rank, Publication ID, DOI, PMID, PMCID, Title, Abstract, Acknowledgements, Source title, Anthology title, Publisher, MeSH terms, PubYear, Publication Date (online), Publication Date (print), Volume, Issue, Pagination, Open Access, Publication Type, Authors, Authors (Raw Affiliation), Corresponding Author, Authors Affiliations, Research Organizations standardized, GRID IDs, City of Research organization, State of Research organization, Country of Research organization, Funder, Funder Group, Funder Country, UIDs of supporting grants, Supporting Grants, Times cited, Recent citations, RCR, FCR, Altmetric, Source Linkout, Dimensions URL, FOR (ANZSRC) Categories, RCDC Categories, HRCS HC Categories, HRCS RAC Categories, ICRP Cancer Types, ICRP CSO Categories, Units of Assessment, Sustainable Development Goals

Figure 4: Metadata Fields in Dimensions

Metadata for article details

The article metadata in databases provides information about article type, DOI, publication date and year etc. Table 1 presents the article metadata fields provided by the three databases. It may be observed that a good number of metadata fields provided by the three databases are common. For example, all the three databases provide fields for document or publication type, publication year, and DOI. However, there are also certain fields that are absent in some database. For example, Language field is not there in Dimensions database, publication date is not there in Scopus and Relevance Rank is not there in Web of Science and Scopus both. The difference in the metadata availability can impact the kind of scientometric analysis possible and/ or the ease of doing such scientometric analysis. Few such cases are discussed next.

Table 1: Metadata Fields for Article Details

Metadata Field	Web of Science	Scopus	Dimensions
Publication Type	PT	-	-
Document Type	DT	Document Type	Publication Type
Language	LA	Language of Original Document	-
Publication Date	PD	-	Publication Date (online), Publication Date (print)
Publication Year	PY	Year	PubYear
Article Number	AR	Art. No.	-
DOI	DI	DOI	DOI
Publication Stage	EA	Publication Stage	-
URL		Link	Source Linkout
PubMed ID	PM	PubMed ID	PMID, PMCID
Database ID	UT	EID	Publication ID
Relevance Rank	-	-	Rank

Remarks: No Language details in Dimensions

The language metadata field of publication records is an important information that can be used to understand the language-wise composition of articles on a research topic or institution- or a country. Since this metadata field is not present in data downloaded from user interface-based search of Dimensions database, a language composition analysis cannot be done with Dimensions data. The publication date is another important field, which unfortunately is missing in Scopus. Therefore, any analysis that requires the publication date of articles cannot be done with data downloaded from Scopus database. One such case may be measuring the speed of accumulation of altmetric mentions, which requires information about article publication date. Another interesting point to observe is that Dimensions database only has limited values of the publication type field and does not provide detailed information like Web of Science. The Web of Science can categorise a publication record as article, review, book chapters, book, proceedings papers etc. However, the Dimensions database does not distinguish between research article and review paper in terms of document type. Further, the percentage of retracted papers can be obtained from Web of Science and Scopus but not from Dimensions because it doesn't contain Retracted paper count.

Metadata for author details

The metadata for author details provided by the three databases is given in table 2. The AU field in Web of Science, Authors field in both Scopus and Dimensions provides the author names separated by a delimiter. This field in all the three databases can be processed to obtain the count of authors in a publication and hence the authorship patterns for the whole set of publication records on a topic or for an institution. However, since, the 'AU' field of Web of

Science contains only initials of authors' first names and not country therefore the 'C1' field in Web of Science which contains the affiliation data has to be used to know the country. These two values together can then be used to determine the gender of the author using a suitable API service. In the case of Scopus, the 'Authors' field as well as 'Authors with Affiliation' field contain the initials of the first name of the authors so these fields cannot be used for gender determination. Dimensions database provides the full first as well as the last name of the authors in the Authors field. It provides the details of the affiliating organization in Authors (Raw Affiliation) field. Moreover, Dimensions database explicitly provides the country of the authors in a dedicated field Research Org Country field. Thus, Dimensions database provides the author related information in a more direct way which can be easily used for tasks like gender determination. Other major difference in Web of Science and the other two databases is that, while Web of Science provides email address, researcher id and ORCID id of the author, these fields are not provided by Scopus and Dimensions database in the downloaded data. Thus, any analysis that requires use or linking of ORCID id of authors can only be done with Web of Science data.

Table 2: Metadata Fields for Author Details

Metadata Field	Web of Science	Scopus	Dimensions
Author Name	AU, AF	Author, Author(s)	Authors
Email Address	EM	-	-
Researcher ID	RI	-	-
Orcid ID	OI	-	-

Remarks: No ORCID ID, Researcher ID and Email in Scopus and Dimensions.

Metadata for research organization details

The metadata fields for obtaining the research organization details of a publication record are provided in table 3. The details comprise of organization name, address and some other identifiers assigned by the database. The Web of Science database provides metadata field 'C1' that contains organization names and addresses (including country) of the authors associated with a publication. Scopus database provides this information in two fields, one containing author names with affiliations and second carrying the affiliation address of the corresponding author. Dimensions database organizes the research organization details in a more structured way. It contains additional fields of standardized organization names, GRID IDs, city, state and country of research organization as separate fields.

Table 3: Metadata Fields for Research Organization Details

Metadata Field	Web of Science	Scopus	Dimensions
Organization Address	C1	Affiliation, Authors with Affiliation	Authors (Raw Affiliation), Author Affiliations
Correspondence Address	-	Correspondence Address	Corresponding Author
Research Organization	-	-	Research Organizations-Standardized
Research Org IDs	-	-	GRID IDs
Research Org City	-	-	City of Research Organization
Research Org State	-	-	State of Research Organization
Research Org Country	-	-	Country of Research Organization

The different metadata fields related to organizations provided by the three databases provide varying possibilities and ease of doing scientometric analysis. For example, Dimensions provide a direct field for country names associated with each publication record. This allows a direct computation of number of internationally collaborated papers in any set of publication records. Further, the proportions of bilateral and multilateral collaborated papers could also be computed directly. Taking other data together (such as for subject area or citations) can further allow a direct computation of impact of international collaboration on citation impact of publications in different subject areas. Dimensions database also provides city and state of publication records. This allows a direct computation of city-wise or state-wise research output, including collaboration patterns in them. Similarly, the standardized organization names and GRID IDs provided by Dimensions database allows a better and easier way to handle duplicate records and organization association problems encountered in Web of Science and Scopus databases. The standardized organization names also allow computation of collaboration patterns in different types of institutions, such as university-industry, university-government, university-facility etc. Thus, in terms of the metadata fields provided for the organization details, Dimensions database may be considered superior in organizing and structuring of the information. Several types of analysis can be conducted using the Dimensions data in a more direct and easy to do manner, which is not possible (or difficult) with Web of Science or Scopus provided metadata.

Metadata for publication source details

The publication source details are provided in the metadata fields of all the three databases. However, they are differently structured. All the three databases provide source title, publisher, volume and page number details of the publication records. Web of Science provides additional information of publisher city and publisher address. The ISSN, abbreviated source name and page count information is provided by both Web of Science and Scopus databases but not by the Dimensions database. Further, Dimensions database does not provide the page count information. Based on the metadata fields provided by the three databases, one may analyse the possibilities and ease of doing scientometric analysis when data is taken from different databases. One such case is that of ISSN, which is not provided by Dimensions database and hence any analysis involving ISSN cannot be done with Dimensions data. Another case, though not that significant is of the page count information, which is provided directly in Web of Science and Scopus but not by Dimensions. Therefore, the average page length of articles in a data set can be more directly computed in Web of Science and Scopus as compared to Dimensions, which will need an extra subtraction operation. There are, however, no other major differences in possibility and ease of doing analysis related to publication source related data from the three databases. The metadata for publication source details found in Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions is provided in table 4.

Table 4: Metadata Fields for Publication Source Details

Metadata Field	Web of Science	Scopus	Dimensions
Publication Source	SO	Source Title	Source title
Publisher Name	PU	Publisher	Publisher
Publisher City	PI	-	-
Publisher Address	PA	-	-
ISSN	SN	ISSN	-
eISSN	EI	-	-
Source Abbreviation	J9, JI	Abbreviated Source Title	-
Volume	VL	Volume	Volume
Issue	IS	Issue	Issue

Beginning Page	BP	Page Start	Pagination
Ending Page	EP	Page End	Pagination
Page Count	PG	Page Count	-

Remarks: No Page Count in Dimensions

Metadata for citation and usage

The citation and article usage details of different kinds is provided in the relevant metadata fields of the three databases. All the three databases provide ‘times cited’ information. Web of Science and Scopus provide ‘cited references’ details of a publication record, which is not provided by Dimensions database user interface-based search. Though a second level search for citation metadata for selected DOIs can be done by using the option ‘Export for bibliometric mapping’. Web of Science exclusively provides usage count information in U1 and U2 fields. It also exclusively provides a cited reference count field. The Dimensions database provides information about recent citations (number of citations accrued by a publication in the last 2 years, reset at the beginning of each calendar year), relative and field weighted citation ratio and the altmetric attention score of a publication record. The table 5 summarizes the citation and usage related metadata fields provided by the three databases.

Table 5: Metadata Fields for Citation, Uses and References

Metadata Field	Web of Science	Scopus	Dimensions
Cited References	CR	References	-
Cited Reference Count	NR	-	-
Times Cited	TC, Z9	Cited by	Times cited
Usage Count	U1, U2	-	-
Recent Citations	-	-	Recent citations
RCR	-	-	RCR
FCR	-	-	FCR
Altmetric	-	-	Altmetric

Remarks: No cited references in Dimensions; No usage count in Scopus and Dimensions

The variation in the citation and usage related metadata fields provided by the three databases allow different possibilities and ease of doing scientometric analysis. The first major observation is that no citation network can be created with data provided by Dimensions database as it does not include cited reference details in publication metadata. A separate download for citation information is required in Dimensions followed by DOI matching process with publications. Further, the usage count-based analysis is possible only with Web of Science database and not with Scopus or Dimensions. U1 reflects the number of times, the full text of a publication record has been downloaded in the last 180 days, U2 counts the number of times the full text of a record has been accessed or saved since February 1, 2013. Studies like Delgado-Lopez-Cozar & Martin-Martin (2016) and Wang et al. (2016) etc. have performed studies on usage count of research articles. Usage count indicator can serve as a metric in determination of latest research fronts (Liang et al., 2017). The correlation between usage and citations for a dataset can also be computed with Web of Science data. In addition, Web of Science provides cited reference count field that can be used to directly compute the average number of references in any dataset being explored, which is otherwise difficult in Scopus and not possible in Dimensions.

The Dimensions database, however, provides altmetric attention score which can be used to do altmetric analysis of a dataset. This is, however, not possible with Web of Science and Scopus. Altmetric attention score can also be used to compute correlations between citations and altmetrics, as seen in some previous studies (Banshal et al., 2021; Costas et al., 2015; Haustein

et al., 2014; Thelwall, 2018b; Thelwall & Nevill, 2018). Moreover, altmetric attention score data has also been used earlier to observe power law behaviours in altmetric data (Banshal et al., 2022).

Similarly, Dimensions provides recent citation, RCR (Relative Citation Ratio) and FCR (Field Citation Ratio) fields, all of which can be used for interesting scientometric analysis. There have been widely acknowledged limitations of using raw citation counts, h-index and Impact Factor in determining research impact (Seglen, 1997; van Yepersele, 2013; Alberts, 2013 etc.). It is because different fields cite at varying rates and citation counts tend to fluctuate in months to years after a publication has occurred. Thus, metrics such as RCR (Relative Citation Ratio) and FCR (Field Citation Ratio) come into play. RCR is obtained by dividing the number of citations an article has received by the expected no. of citations of the articles, while FCR is obtained by the average journal citation rate of the articles of the same field. A discussion of citation metrics such as RCR, FWCI (Field weighted citation impact) has been provided in the study by Purkasthya et al. (2019). A thorough discussion of such metrics could also be found in studies like Waltman & Van Eck (2015), Janssens et al., (2017) and Bloudoff-Indelicato (2015), Bornmann and Haunschild (2017). The Dimensions database is thus well-suited for this kind of analysis as it explicitly contains the metadata for both the RCR and FCR values of a publication record.

Metadata for funding acknowledgements

The funding and grant details for different publication records is captured by the databases in different metadata fields. The table 6 presents the metadata fields for funding acknowledgement in the three databases. The Web of Science and Scopus databases both contain funding details and a funding acknowledgement text. Dimensions database contains some additional information in form of funding country and grant IDs. In Web of Science, the funding details i.e. the Funder Agency name and Grant No. is provided in 'FU' field like "*National Natural Science Foundation of China [71904081]; Chinese Education Department Research Foundation for Humanities and Social Sciences [19YJC870017]*" while the textual details on acknowledging the funder of the publication is provided in the 'FX' field like "*Yi Bu acknowledges financial support from the National Natural Science Foundation of China (No. 71904081) and the Chinese Education Department Research Foundation for Humanities and Social Sciences (No. 19YJC870017).*" In the Scopus database, the 'Funding Details' field contains data as "*Ministerio de Ciencia y Tecnología, \xa0MICYT: 1FD97-0931, \xa0PB1998-1293*" while 'Funding Text 1/2/3/4' metadata fields contain acknowledgement details to the funder as "*This study was supported by the Spanish Ministry of Science and Technology through projects no. 1FD97-0931 and PB1998-1293.*" The grant numbers and the funding agency can be extracted from these metadata fields from Scopus database. The Dimensions database on the other hand contains multiple metadata fields that contain information explicitly on grant numbers like 'Supporting Grants' and 'UIDs of supporting grants' fields; the name of country that funds in the field 'Funding Country' as "*Germany; Germany*"; the name of funding agencies and group of funding agencies in 'Funder' and 'Funder Group' fields as "*German Academic Exchange Service; Federal Ministry of Education and Research*", "*AMRC - Association of Medical Research Charities; cOAlition S; ICRP - International Cancer Research Partnership*"; the text acknowledging the funder in 'Acknowledgements field' as "*This article is a substantially extended version of the paper Zhao et al. (2021) presented at the 18th International Conference on Scientometrics and Informetrics (ISSI 2021). The authors highly appreciate the comments from anonymous reviewers, the suggestions from Rezvaneh Rezapour, and the technical support from Tom Theile.*"

Table 6: Metadata Fields for Funding Acknowledgements

Metadata Field	Web of Science	Scopus	Dimensions
Funding Agency and Grant Number	FU	Funding Details	Funder, Funder Group
Funding Text	FX	Funding Text	Acknowledgements
Funding Country	-	-	Funding Country
Supporting GRANT ID	-	-	Supporting Grants, UIDs of supporting grants

It is known that research funding and incentives to institutions/universities bolsters publication performance (Auranen & Nieminen, 2010; Hicks, 2012; Bloch & Sorensen, 2015 etc.). Further, it is expected that publicly funded research output should be openly accessible. For these and other purposes the funding metadata is analysed in several studies. Patterns of funded publication in a given dataset are often analysed along with other relevant fields like citations, subject area, country. While Web of Science and Scopus provide similar metadata and hence similar analysis possible, Dimensions provides a more structured metadata for funding details. Funding country and ID are two additional fields in Dimensions, which can be used for country details of funding agencies and resultant publications in different subject areas.

Metadata for textual details

There are some text related metadata of articles provided by the three databases. These include author keywords, index keywords, abstract and title of the article. The Web of Science and Scopus databases provide all these four fields. However, Dimensions only provides title and abstract fields. The table 7 summarizes the text-related metadata provided by the three databases. The textual information provided is not only used in retrieval related queries but also for the purposes of creating keyword co-occurrence networks. The keywords (both author and index) have been used in many previous studies for tasks as versatile as keyword density mapping to creation of expertise indices (Lathabai, Nandy & Singh, 2021) and their applications (Lathabai, Nandy & Singh, 2022). Keywords and index keywords are also used to understand the thematic structure of research publications and draw visualization maps. While all this analysis is possible with data from Web of Science and Scopus databases, it would not be possible with Dimensions database. The Dimensions database does not provide keywords in user interface-based search and hence any analysis involving keywords is not possible if the data is obtained from Dimensions database.

Table 7: Metadata Fields for Text and Keywords

Metadata Field	Web of Science	Scopus	Dimensions
Author Keywords	DE	Author Keywords	-
Index Keywords	ID	Index Keywords	-
Abstract	AB	Abstract	Abstract
Title	TI	Title	Title

Remarks: No keywords in Dimensions

Metadata for open access details

The scholarly databases nowadays also contain information about open access availability of articles. The table 8 shows the metadata fields provided for the purpose by the three databases. It can be observed that all the three databases provide details about open access availability of a publication. The Web of Science 'OA' field contains data like "gold, Green Published, Green Submitted". The Scopus 'Open Access' field contains data like "All Open Access, Bronze,

Green” and Dimensions contains data like “*All OA; Green*” in the ‘Open Access’ field. Thus, the three databases contain open access status of publication records separated by identifiers like ‘,’ and ‘;’ which can be easily processed to obtain the open access status of publication records.

Table 8: Metadata Fields for Open Access

Metadata Field	Web of Science	Scopus	Dimensions
OA Category	OA	Open Access	Open Access

It is known that institutions across countries are now increasingly participating in open access publishing (Sun et al., 2015) and that open access availability enhances greater participation in science for various audiences such as authors, researchers, funders etc. (Laakso et al., 2011). It is particularly beneficial for developing and under-developed countries (Chan et al., 2005). There are different routes to open access, such as Gold, Green, Bronze etc. (Piwowar et al., 2018). Owing to importance associated with open access, several previous studies have tried to measure the extent and the type of open access publishing at the level of a country by using the open access related metadata field (Singh et al., 2020a; Srichandan et al., 2020). Though different studies may have used different database, there is no difference in the databases regarding the open access related metadata and hence any of them can be used for open access related analysis with the same ease.

Metadata for conference details

The scholarly databases include metadata fields for conferences and articles published in their proceedings. The table 9 summarizes the conference related metadata fields provided by the three databases. The Web of Science provides information about conference title, year, location etc. The Scopus database also provides information related to conference name, date and location. Both databases also provide for a conference code. However, while Web of Science provides for conference year, Scopus provides conference dates. The Dimensions database on the other hand does not provide any conference related metadata. Though it provides a filter for conference search by searching for proceedings, but conference details metadata is not provided. Therefore, any analysis involving conference publications can be done only by using data from Web of Science or Scopus databases and data downloaded from Dimensions cannot be used for this purpose.

Table 9: Metadata Fields for Conference Details

Metadata Field	Web of Science	Scopus	Dimensions
Conference Title	CT	Conference name	-
Conference Year	CY	Conference date	-
Conference Location	CL	Conference location	-
Conference Sponsor	SP	-	-
Conference Host	HO	-	-
Conference Code	-	Conference code	-

Remarks: No conference details metadata in Dimensions

Metadata for subject categories

The scholarly databases provide for different kinds of subject classification of publication records. The table 9 summarizes the metadata fields related to subject classification in the three databases. The Web of Science provides a ‘WC’ field which contains an entry for Web of Science subject category. There are about 258 subject categories provided by Web of Science. This field contains the following types of subject categories- “*Computer Science, Artificial*

Intelligence; Computer Science, Information Systems; Computer Science, Theory & Methods” etc. The Web of Science also provides a metadata field ‘SC’ (Research Area) which provides a top-level subject classification. The Scopus database, however, doesn’t provide any metadata on subject classification in the downloaded publication metadata. Although Scopus provides for 27 subject categories, it only allows searching by them in user interface and does not include information about the subject category in the metadata that is downloaded. The Dimensions database contains provides a metadata field ‘FOR (ANZSRC Categories)’ which is one of the major subject categories provided in the Dimensions database. The entries for this field comprise of a code and subject name, such as 40 Engineering, 31 Biological Science, 46 Information and Computing Sciences etc. The Fields of Research Classification (FoR), a part of the 2020 Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC) system⁶ has three hierarchical-levels namely Divisions, Groups and Fields. While Division represents a broad subject area, groups and fields represent detailed subsets of these areas. The Division and Group level of FoR has been emulated by Dimensions based on a machine-learning approach. The implementation in Dimensions is categorised in 2-digit and 4-digit codes in which records are classified into 22 Divisions and 171 Groups. This database, however, also provides alignment with many national subject classification schemes too. A previous study provides a good comparative analysis of the subject classification schemes of the three databases (Singh et al., 2020b). The Dimensions database also provides a classification/ tagging of publication records on sustainable development goals.

Table 10: Metadata Fields for Subject Categories

Metadata Field	Web of Science	Scopus	Dimensions
Subject Category	WC	-	FOR (ANZSRC Categories), RCDC Categories, HRCS HC Categories, HRCS RAC Categories, ICRP Cancer Types, ICRP CSO Categories, Units of Assessment
Research Area	SC	-	-
Sustainable Development Goals	-	-	Sustainable Development Goals

Classification of research articles into different subject areas is an extremely important task in bibliometric analysis and information retrieval. There are primarily two kinds of subject classification approaches used in different academic databases: journal-based (aka source-level) and article-based (aka publication-level). The two popular academic databases- Web of Science and Scopus- use journal-based subject classification scheme for articles, which assigns articles into a subject based on the subject category assigned to the journal in which they are published. On the other hand, the Dimensions database uses article-based subject classification scheme that assigns the article to a subject category based on its contents.

The availability of subject classification metadata is very important for the purpose of finding subject area distribution of publications from an institution, subject area distribution of highly cited publications, subject area-wise differentiation of open access patterns etc. Both, Web of Science and Dimensions metadata can be used for such analysis, however, Scopus metadata cannot be used for the purpose. Similarly, if it is required to identify the major subject areas

⁶<https://www.abs.gov.au/statistics/classifications/australian-and-new-zealand-standard-research-classification-anzsrc>

contributing to research in an emerging topic (such as Artificial Intelligence or Quantum Computing), the subject classification metadata will be required for the analysis. Therefore, metadata provided by Scopus database cannot be used for such a study.

Dimensions database provides the additional tagging of publication records into various SDGs (Sustainable Development Goals). This tagging can be used for identifying major subject areas that contribute to research in a given SDG. Similarly, a country-specific publication analysis on SDGs can also be done by using Dimensions data, as demonstrated in (Singh, Kanaujia & Singh, 2022).

Practical implications

The analysis of metadata provided by the three databases have shown that some kinds of scientometric analysis is not possible with metadata provided by a database. The analysis has also shown that there is an ease of doing different scientometric analysis if metadata from a particular database is used. This section presents a summary of such analysis, focusing mainly on the practical implications.

Analysis of possibilities of scientometric analysis

- The language composition analysis of publication records in a dataset is not possible with Dimensions provided metadata. Therefore, if language of publications is to be analysed, then either Web of Science or Scopus should be used.
- Dimensions database does not distinguish between research article and review paper in terms of document type and hence proportion of research articles and review papers in a dataset cannot be obtained from Dimensions provided metadata.
- The publication date of articles is not provided in the Scopus metadata and therefore an analysis involving use of the publication date information (such as to measure the speed of accumulation of altmetric mentions or citations) cannot be done with Scopus. For such analysis, Web of Science metadata should be used.
- The percentage of retracted papers can be obtained only from Web of Science and Scopus and not from Dimensions as it does not have such type of information included. Therefore, Web of Science or Scopus should be used for retraction analysis.
- Scopus database provides only initials of the first name of the authors and therefore it cannot be used to determine gender of authors by using some API service. Hence, for the purposes of gender-based analysis of research publication, either Web of Science or Dimensions should be used.
- Both Scopus and Dimensions do not provide ORCID id information of authors. Therefore, any analysis involving some linkage with ORCID id should use only Web of Science data.
- The Dimensions database does not provide ISSN information in its metadata and therefore either Web of Science or Scopus data can be used for any analysis involving ISSN information.
- The analysis of usage of articles requires usage count information, which is provided by Web of Science database only and not by Scopus or Dimensions. Therefore, only Web of Science data can be used for article usage analysis.
- Altmetric analysis of publication records can only be done with Dimensions database as it is the only database providing altmetric attention score. The Web of Science and Scopus databases cannot be used for this purpose.
- The Dimensions database does not provide author or index keywords in user interface-based search and hence any analysis involving keywords (such as identifying thematic patterns and trends, co-word analysis etc.) is not possible with Dimensions database, leaving the choice of using either Web of Science or Scopus database.

- The Dimensions database cannot be used for an analysis of conference publications as it does not provide metadata about conferences. The Web of Science or Scopus database can be used for the purpose, though Scopus should be a preferred choice as it provides information about conference date whereas Web of Science only provides year information only.
- The Scopus metadata cannot be used for analysis involving subject category differentiation as it does not provide any metadata on subject classification in the downloaded publication metadata. Either Web of Science or Dimensions database can be used for such analysis.
- Dimensions database provides the additional tagging of publication records into various SDGs. This tagging can be used for identifying major subject areas that contribute to research in each SDG. Similarly, a country-specific publication analysis on SDGs can also be done by using Dimensions data. This analysis at present is not possible with metadata provided by Web of Science or Scopus.

Analysis of ease of doing scientometric analysis

- Dimensions database explicitly provides the country of the authors in a dedicated field Research Org Country field, making analysis of ICP (Internationally Collaborated Papers) patterns easier. Similarly, Dimensions also provides a direct field for country names associated with each publication record. This allows a direct computation of number of internationally collaborated papers in any set of publication records. Thus, international collaboration patterns in a data (including proportion of bilateral and multilateral collaborated papers) can be more easily computed using Dimensions data.
- Dimensions database also provides city and state of publication records. This allows a direct computation of city-wise or state-wise research output, including collaboration patterns in them. The use of Web of Science or Scopus for the purpose will need additional string processing to extract such information. Therefore, Dimensions provides an ease of analysis in this regard.
- The Dimensions database also provides standardized organization names with unique GRID Ids and organization type. This information makes it easier to compute university-industry, university-government, university-facility research collaboration. The use of Web of Science and Scopus data for this requires additional effort.
- The average page length of articles in a data set can be more directly computed in Web of Science and Scopus as compared to Dimensions, which will need an extra subtraction operation.
- Any analysis involving creation of citation network cannot be done easily with Dimensions publication metadata as it does not include cited reference details in the publication metadata. A separate download for citation metadata is required, which must be then matched with publication metadata through DOI matching. Therefore, for analysis involving co-citations or bibliographic coupling, Web of Science or Scopus database may be a preferred choice, if coverage is not an issue.
- The Web of Science provides cited reference count field, which can be used to directly compute the average number of references in any dataset being explored, which is otherwise difficult in Scopus and not possible in Dimensions.
- Dimensions provide a more structured metadata for funding details. Funding country and ID are two additional fields in Dimensions, which can be used for country details of funding agencies and resultant publications in different subject areas

Conclusion

The study presented an analysis of metadata fields provided by the three scholarly databases- Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions. It analysed the metadata fields obtained through user interface-based search in the three databases. These metadata fields are then grouped into various categories and the metadata fields in each group are compared across the three databases. Thus, the study provides a detailed account of the major metadata fields in data obtained from UI based search in Web of Science, Scopus and Dimensions and analyses how much do the metadata fields differ across databases (RQ1). The analysis shows that different databases have some variations in the metadata fields provided in a publication record download from user interface-based search. Therefore, the effect of presence or absence of a metadata field on the possibility or ease of doing scientometric analysis is undertaken and key findings are summarized under the section on practical implications (RQ2). The findings can be useful for scientometric researchers, practitioners, and managers of these databases in various ways.

Limitations and future work

The study is first of its kind to have analysed the metadata of the three important scholarly databases and there lies its novelty. However, the study only compares the metadata fields obtained through user interface-based search from the three databases. Since the databases provide different ways of access (such as through user interface or APIs), the functionalities and capabilities of scientometric analysis may vary with different forms of access. For example, the Dimensions database provides a very rich metadata through API based download, which is not only more structured but also provides more possibilities and ease of doing scientometric analysis as compared to user interface-based data download. Therefore, the metadata fields obtained through API-based data download can also be compared.

Another important aspect that this study has not addressed is the completeness of metadata fields provided by the three scholarly databases. It has been found in earlier studies (such as Maddi & Badoin, 2022) that all metadata fields provided by a database are not always populated with data for a given set of publication records and that there are missing values. For example, on a sample dataset obtained for a query “sentiment analysis”, we found that the metadata field for ‘DOI’ in Web of Science was 96% populated, in Scopus it was 80% populated and in Dimensions it was 90% populated. Similarly, the metadata for obtaining author address was 99% populated in Web of Science, 94% in Scopus and 61% in Dimensions. The Dimensions database provide unique metadata fields for city, state, and country of research organization, but the fields are not always populated with data. For example, for a query “sentiment analysis” with Dimensions UI, the obtained data has city details populated in only 62% publication records, state details for only 36% publication records and country for only 61% publication records.

Thus, it may be the case that in theory a database provides a metadata field, but in practice most of that metadata field may have missing values. Therefore, in actual practice not only the availability of a metadata field in a database matter for scientometric analysis, but the population of the metadata field is equally important. More research can be done in this direction to understand the impact of not only the availability of metadata fields but also the availability of data in them on the possibilities and the ease of doing scientometric assessment exercises.

Declarations

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